

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetics

Genetic parameters of submergence tolerance in some rainfed lowland rices of Bangladesh

M. S. Pathan and N. M. Miah, Plant Breeding Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Gazipur 1701, Bangladesh

We used five rainfed lowland rice cultivars—one resistant, two moderately resistant, and two susceptible to submergence (FR13A, Dudmona, Kumragoir, Nizersail, and BR5)—to make one-way diallel crosses without reciprocal in 1983-85.

The ratios of submergence tolerance showed that dominant components were highly significant (see table), indicating the important role of additive as well as dominant genes. The dominance ratio $(H_1/D)^{1/2}$ of 0.55 (partial dominance) was also supported by graphic analysis (see figure). The proportion of the gene in the parents $(H_2/4H_1)$ showed some degree of gene asymmetry in favor of recessive alleles, as evidenced by the negative sign of F. The dominant and

Genetic parameters of submergence tolerance and their ratios. Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1983-85.

Genetic parameter	Estimates ^a
D (additive)	4.031** ± 0.038
H ₁ (dominance)	1.229** ± 0.278
H ₂ (dominance)	1.291** ± 0.229
h ² (dominance)	1.356** ± 0.104
F (additive, dominance, and gene asymmetry)	-1.444 ± 0.238
E (environment)	0.042 ± 0.006
$(H_1/D)^{1/2}$ (average dominance)	0.552
$(H_2/4H_1)$ (gene asymmetry)	0.263
h ² /H ₂ (number of gene blocks)	1.050
$\frac{1}{2}D + \frac{1}{2}H_1 - \frac{1}{2}H_2 - \frac{1}{2}F$	0.880
$(\frac{1}{2}D + \frac{1}{2}H_1 - \frac{1}{2}H_2 - \frac{1}{2}F) + E$ (narrow-sense heritability)	

^a**Significant at the 0.01 level.

Covariance (Wr)/variance (Vr) regression of submergence tolerance. Parents are 1) BR5, 2) Nizersail, 3) Kumragoir, 4) Dudmona, and 5) FR13A.

recessive genes were in unequal proportions in the parent (ratio 0.51).

The ratio of h^2/H_2 was 1.05, suggesting involvement of at least 1 major gene or a group of genes having partial dominance. The Vr, Wr graph analysis shows that the parents FR13A possesses the most resistant alleles and BR5 and Nizersail possess susceptible alleles for submergence tolerance. The high narrow-sense heritability (0.88) showed the importance of additive gene action in submergence tolerance. □

Combining ability of upland rice progenitors

E. P. Guimarães, EMBRAPA/Centro Nacional de Pesquisa de Arroz e Feijão (CNPAP), Caixa Postal 179, 74000 Goiânia, GO, Brazil

In the 1987-88 season, 140 F₂ upland rice populations were evaluated in the CNPAP breeding program; 79 were discarded due to neck blast (Bl) susceptibility.

To study combining ability, the progenitors crossed at least 7 times were chosen from the total 63 used to make

Combining ability of upland rice progenitors. CNPAP, Brazil, 1987-88.

Progenitor	Populations (no.)		Populations (no.) with phenotypic variability			Neck Bl	
	Selected	Discarded	High	Medium	Low	Average	Range
Araguaia	8	1	1	8	0	4.2	3.0-6.0
A8-204-1	10	0	3	6	1	4.8	4.0-6.0
Cuiabana	8	0	1	6	1	4.1	3.0-5.0
IRAT216	10	0	3	6	1	5.1	3.0-6.0
Cabapu	7	2	4	3	2	5.2	3.0-7.0
CNA4640	7	2	2	5	2	5.3	3.0-8.0
CNA5180	7	2	4	3	2	5.2	3.0-7.0
IAC82-276	6	1	0	1	6	5.0	3.0-7.0
CNA4157	2	5	3	1	3	6.9	6.0-8.0
Mut. Makouta 41-1-3	3	4	1	0	6	5.3	4.0-7.0
TOm 1-3	2	5	7	0	0	6.7	5.0-8.0
Apura (indica group)	1	10	11	0	0	6.9	6.0-8.0